

Impact of Movies on Adolescents

Mary K.M¹, Dr. Reeta Sexena²

¹PhD scholar in Sociology, School of Arts and Humanities, Career Point University, Kota, Rajasthan, Email: marykm_13@yahoo.in

²Associate Professor Department of Sociology, Career Point University Kota, Rajasthan, India Email: drreetasaxena@gmail.com

Abstract

Adolescents love movies. Movies are of a great source of information and knowledge. They can contribute to the life of adolescents in various ways. Movies have taken a significant place in education field too. Also, there are many learning happens when we watch a movie. Unfortunately, majority of our adolescents consider movies as leisure, fun activity. It is a fact that movies influence the imagination and thoughts of adolescents. Imitation is a tendency that develops in the adolescence age. They love to imitate the actions and behaviors of their onscreen heroes and heroines. But the adolescents lack realization that these particular characters are scripted for a particular movie and once these roles are played, the actors or actresses have nothing to do with that character. There are positive as well as negative impact in the personality and life of adolescents when they watch movies. So empowering the adolescents by the parents is very important to accept or reject an idea or a new learning before they emulate it. This empowerment can be done through regular open dialogues and brainstorming between the adolescents and parents in the families. It will develop a feeling of freedom in the adolescents to open their minds and share their views in the family.

Key words:

Movies, adolescence, Influences, reinforce, inspire, and contribute, educational, negative effects, aggressive, fascinated, pleasure oriented, powerful visuals, imitating tendency, awareness and motivation, sexual immoralities.

Introduction

Movies have been one of the greatest influences in modern life. It's the combination of technology, business, entertainment and artistic. Each of the above has an important role in the present day of world. A movie derives its ideas and imaginations from its surroundings.

It has transformed itself to a virtual way of life. It provides a platform that reflects the growth of the economy, politics, and technological advancements. Films are also useful for

knowing the history of the ancient world. The images movies create; need to be in synchronized with the expectations and needs of the society. A movie is not only a visual treat to its audience but it is also an account of the societal, economical and political set up in which we are living. Movies are powerful platform that can exert influence in the young minds. Movies make

intricate issues easier to understand. Movies can cause people especially adolescents to think seriously about something.

Positive effects of movies on adolescent's life

Movies can reinforce to develop and accelerate adolescent's cognitive skills such as long-term memory, sustained attention, logical reasoning, creativity etc. Movies enables the young minds to reflect upon complex subjects such as governance, economic system, inequality, environmental concerns, social justice, gender bias etc. They can assist the economy to grow, inspire individuals to live a quality good life and increase the knowledge of the world around us. They provide enjoyment and they are good for stress reduction and relaxation. Many times, movies show us positive ways to resolve the problems in our life. Sometimes movies teach us the ways to cope up with various life situations. Movies can inspire our life many ways and they can shape our beliefs and values. Good movies even help to shape the personality and character of growing adolescent by motivating to adapt good traits. They help to unlearn and make room for new things. Movies provide new knowledge and exposure to many unknown areas that can really contribute to our life. Movies bring forward many conversation scenes that can help to introduce new vocabulary, and standard pronunciation which is helpful for the adolescents.

Movies can provide educational resources. They can improve the language skill of the adolescents in a motivating way while enjoying a movie. Movies use phrases in many situations and they make easier to understand. Movies also teach how to use the words and phrases in communication. Since adolescents are quick minded with good grasping power, they can easily add new words and phrases to their vocabulary from these visuals. Movies combined with regular teaching helps students to gain deeper understanding. It also helps in understanding and grasping the content easier if it does not deviate from the facts. Movies allow students to see the lives of different characters, living in different of the world. Films provide a visual aid to understand historical events. Comparing to the past, education has surpassed the traditional and orthodox methods of teaching. Using technology to provide knowledge was an unattainable dream earlier. Today, the technology is getting more upgraded, with modern concept of making use of movies as a tool in providing education.

Movies enable students to learn visually as the texts do. If we take biographic movies as an example, the students can view a recreation of the person whose life is sketched in that biography. The visuals provide a deeper understanding about the time, era and the lifestyle of the historical figure than simple words. Books have many limitations than the movies. It needs quality time to read and comprehend a book because they have a large number of pages. Educational movies known as documentaries are also used as educational resource. These documentaries are shown to the students in the schools for

educational purpose. Documentaries are also used in teachers training. Various developmental organizations and cooperative sectors also use documentaries in their human resource trainings, executive meetings etc. Documentaries are also used to educate and create awareness in rural population about various developmental issues. Students respond better to watching movies than reading which prevent them from getting distracted easily. This is effective for those who are not motivated readers. Students especially children and adolescents with learning disabilities show a response to movies and can relate to them. Movies can be an efficient method of education. But, there are still several challenges which it needs to overcome, to be accepted universally.

Negative effects of movies on adolescents

Movies can also affect the people, especially adolescents in negative way. Viewing movies with sex, violence, drug abuse, adult themes and offensive language have a negative effect on children and adolescents. Many movies are not appropriate to watch for children and adolescents. They can influence the thinking and behavior of children and adolescents and can lead to negative outcomes. Movies can create violence which is often driven by negative emotions. Children especially adolescents get influenced by the thriller or crime oriented movies. They develop tendency to become aggressive. Adolescents have a tendency to imitate anything that is attractive to them. Thus movies characters become role models for adolescents and they imitate their fashions, actions and behaviors.

Today's movies demonstrate more advanced fashions and trends to which the young generations are fascinated. These movies are promoting the concept of pleasure oriented lifestyles. Too much exposure in movies develops false good illusions in the minds of the young generation and they adopt those styles and fashions even it is not suiting to them. Thus they give a bad impression about their dressing sense that reflects their personality, character, mood, style and what they are actually as an individual. The most important about the movies is that they send messages to the public. A good number of movies glorify the alcohol consumption, substance abuse, adultery and fornication through its dialogues and scenes. They provide opportunities to watch scenes of sexual immoralities, which is a disaster for the children, adolescents and for the society itself.

Concepts like live in relationship, premarital sex, gay marriages, single parenting, Substance addiction, alcoholism etc. are example for wrong practices that is cultivated by the movies. Teenage romance and relationships is the another negative effect movies cause in adolescents life. This pleasure oriented lifestyle give the young generation an impression that life is all about personal freedom and giving more importance to one's own likes and choices. Thus there is a gross reduction in personal as well as social values in the society. As a result of it, the marriages are struggling to survive, divorce are increasing, number of broken families are increasing. The family is the very basic unit of the society and many families are deteriorating its glory. Joint family system is disappearing slowly in which there was a wonderful atmosphere for the children and adolescents to grow and develop. Numbers of nuclear families are increasing. Above all, there is a hike in the number of single parenting.

Movie is a work of visual art that replicate human experiences reflecting the world and the

time in which we live. They also communicate ideas, stories perceptions, feelings, beauty and atmosphere through moving images. The visual images are very powerful. The human brain process images around 60,000 times faster than text. The picture superiority effect tells us that images are more memorable than text. The eidetic memory which is also known as photographic memory with high precision has the ability to recall an image from memory at least for a short period. So adolescents are easily slipped in to the inclination to imitate the screen heroes and heroines in their everyday life. Since visual images are very powerful, adolescents get trapped by the imitating tendency. Generally, adolescents and youngsters have the craze to watch movies. They spend a good amount of money for it. This craze also results in considerable waste of their precious time which otherwise could have invested for fulfilling their tasks. The schools, teachers and parents put their maximum efforts to teach and inculcate good habits, and develop good character in adolescents by their persistent advises, guidance and instructions. But, it does not bring much result as the young minds are in the grip of movies and fashion craze. Watching films frequently can affect the adolescent's character and morals adversely.

Adolescence is a period of significant development. It also has to perform certain tasks associated with the next period or stage in life. Successful achievement of a certain task is expected to lead to happiness and to success with later tasks, while failure may result in unhappiness in the individual, disapproval by the society and difficulty with later tasks. A large number of youngsters are trapped in the movie and fashion world and unable to do anything fruitful. Thus there is a big financial decline in the families and difficulty to meet their requirement of decent quality life.

As a result of watching movies adolescents often involves exploring physical intimacy, sexual feelings and sexual attraction. Adolescent's romance is motivated by the romancing of actors and actresses they watch on screen. This causes the adolescents to view sex in very casual manner. Adolescence is a period of imitation and looking for new experience. Therefore the content of romantic movies they watch can be harmful for them if they are not guided properly. In many families, parents spend very little time with their adolescents. Many parents do not ask to their adolescents about their ideas, views on topics like romance, relationships etc. Since they do not create any space for the adolescents for a friendly conversation, or open discussion, the adolescents do not get proper guidance from the parents during their formative years.

How to overcome negative effect of movies in adolescents?

Adolescence is a stage of life with full of energy and enthusiasm. It is a stage of learning and performing multiple tasks simultaneously. Open, non-judgmental family discussions about relationships can encourage adolescents to share their opinions and views in the family. Hormonal changes triggered by brain and body developments also cause for a longing for intimacy and support from opposite sex. Timely attention of parents to direct and channelize adolescent's energy of mind with suitable creative activities may bring positive outcomes. Frequent brainstorming in the families in various topics can develop transparency and better understanding in related subjects. Such initiatives may reduce the

peer group influence over the minds of adolescents. As a result of it, the adolescents–parents relationship in the families will become stronger and it will also boost the confidence in the adolescents.

Conclusion

Movies are source of social awareness and motivation. To achieve goals, adolescents can absorb the information; knowledge and learning that are useful for their life from good movies. The adolescents should also learn to reject all those which are garbage when it comes to a disciplined life. To enable the adolescents to do such selections or rejections, they should have a thorough understanding about the negative and positive effect of movies in different areas of their life. Everything has something good as well as bad in it. It depends on us what we are choosing.

References:

<https://www.momspresso.com/parenting/275d636dd6a24caeb7ecae4066b83fe4/article/negative-impact-of-movies-on-youth-nv1kztm41y4j>

https://www.google.com/search?q=negative+impact+of+movies+on+youth&ei=TY--ZifBHoiu2roP6bGkmAM&oq=movies+impact+on+adolescent&gs_l=lp=Egxd3Mtd2l6LXNlcnAiGm

<https://filminutz.in/how-movies-affect-society-the-good-the-bad-and-the-ugly/#:~:text=Another%20way%20that%20movies%20can,a%20negative%20impact%20on%20society.>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC72881>

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